

**MYTHOLOGICAL ELEMENTS AND THEIR FUNCTION IN
CONTEMPORARY ENGLISH AND UZBEK FICTION**

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In mythological legends, the connection of events with great water, fire, flood, supernatural power, giant figure, god, miracle of the Pirs increased the power of influence, gaining faith, and belief in the 12 gods, served as an incentive. In short, these myths describe the family, the tribe, the beliefs, and the characteristics of this type of myth. Titan heroes emerged as the creators of goodness, the symbol of fire, the element of water, the gods of fertility, and the worship of supernatural beings in their time, encouraging them to consider it sacred, strengthened faith, and finally the epic tradition of each allowed to form as. The origin of this type of myth was based on the influence of dualism, the constant conflict between the gods of good and evil. This is described in mythological legends as the intertwining of the two gods. Qayumars, the god of goodness, at the same time, acts as a creator, Ahraman, the god of evil, the destroyer. In battle, Qayumars is defeated and given peace, tranquility, and abundance. Legends call for the belief in the god of goodness and the worship of his blessings. The great ideas are conveyed on the scale of fighting against tyranny. These kinds of legends have an ancient history and are based on an unconscious attitude to the phenomena of nature and society, reflecting social thinking, various rituals, concepts, some elements of patron cults. Most importantly, this type of myth is characterized by mythological concepts, beliefs in cults, and the ability to describe the causes of the emergence of nature, the characteristics of primitive society. They are simple concepts, trying to determine the cause of a factor in the occurrence of strange symptoms.

Mythology is primarily an artistic reflection of the thinking of primitive society. The earliest mythology served as the main source for the emergence, formation and development of artistic creation, especially folklore. Analyzes show that mythology has traversed a long historical period as the basis of primitive culture, the dominant idea of the ideology of the tribal period. It is the product of primitive thinking, which is the unconscious artistic thinking based on the tribal ideas of primitive people about the universe. Mythology is the same truth for the creator of myths.

Mythological images are mythological characters that have a mythological basis in folklore, oral art, written literature, and works of art. Mythological images are an animated symbolic representation of a particular event, which conveys the essence of reality in a metaphorical, symbolic and allegorical state, and is its formal embodiment. Mythological images are the product of primitive artistic fiction, various phenomena in the universe, nature and society, had served to explain the causes of the supernatural forces that exist in the human imagination. After the formation of artistic thinking, mythological images, which are an integral part of mythology, have moved into literature and art. These include works of Uzbek classical literature, epics from the series "Alpomish", "Kuntugmish", "Rustamkhan" and "Gorogly", mythological images in Uzbek folklore, legends and fairy tales. Mythological images in folklore and written literature serve to show the full expression of artistic interpretation and the breadth of poetic thinking. Kayumars, Anaxita, Akhriman, giant, fairy, dragon related to Avesto myths in Uzbek folklore; water cult related Hubby, Sust wife, Water wife, Half wife; Haydar, Yalli momo, Naked father, Choymomo, imagined as the "piri" of the wind; Ayamajuz, Aziz momo, Ahman Dahman related to the national calendar; thunder, and lightning "owner" Guldur momo; Adam Ad, Olangasar, Dorokoz, described as legendary heroes; there are many heroes, such as monsters and monsters, who express their views on evil forces.

Mythological elements have been present in literature for centuries, and their function in contemporary English and Uzbek fiction is no different. These elements serve to add depth and meaning to the stories being told, as well as to connect readers to the cultural and historical context of the works.

In English fiction, mythological elements are often used to explore universal themes and archetypes. For example, J.K. Rowling's Harry Potter series draws heavily on mythological creatures such as dragons and centaurs, as well as on the concept of the hero's journey. These elements add a sense of wonder and magic to the story, while also providing readers with a framework for understanding the characters' struggles and triumphs.

Similarly, in Uzbek fiction, mythological elements are used to connect readers to the country's rich cultural heritage. For example, Chingiz Aitmatov's novel "The Day Lasts More Than a Hundred Years" draws on traditional myths and legends to explore themes of identity, tradition, and modernity. By incorporating these elements into his work, Aitmatov is able to create a sense of continuity between Uzbekistan's past and present.

Overall, mythological elements play an important role in contemporary English and Uzbek fiction. They serve to enrich the stories being told, connect readers to cultural and historical context, and explore universal themes and archetypes. As such, they are an essential tool for writers seeking to create meaningful and impactful works of literature.

Myths and mythological images have been present in English literature for centuries. In the medieval period, writers such as Chaucer and Shakespeare drew on classical myths and legends to explore themes of love, power, and fate. The Renaissance saw a renewed interest in classical mythology, with writers such as Edmund Spenser and John Milton incorporating mythological elements into their works.

In the 19th century, the Romantic poets drew on mythology to express their ideas about nature, imagination, and the divine. Percy Bysshe Shelley's "Prometheus Unbound" and John Keats' "Endymion" are examples of works that use mythological imagery to explore these themes.

In the 20th century, modernist writers such as T.S. Eliot and James Joyce used mythological elements to create complex and layered works of literature. Eliot's "The Waste Land" draws on a range of mythological traditions to explore the fragmented and disorienting nature of modern life, while Joyce's "Ulysses" uses the structure of Homer's *Odyssey* to explore the inner lives of its characters.

Contemporary English literature continues to draw on mythology to explore universal themes and create engaging and impactful works. The Harry Potter series, for example, has become a cultural phenomenon by drawing on a range of mythological creatures and concepts to create a rich and immersive world. Other contemporary writers, such as Neil Gaiman and Margaret Atwood, also draw on mythology to create compelling stories that resonate with readers.

In contemporary English literature, mythological elements serve a variety of functions. They can be used to create a sense of depth and richness in a fictional world, as seen in the Harry Potter series. By drawing on a range of mythological creatures and concepts, J.K. Rowling creates a vivid and immersive world that feels both familiar and unique.

Mythological elements can also be used to explore universal themes and ideas. Neil Gaiman's *American Gods*, for example, uses mythological figures from a range of cultures to explore the nature of belief and the clash between old and new gods. Margaret Atwood's *The Penelopiad* retells the story of Homer's

Odyssey from the perspective of Penelope, exploring themes of gender, power, and agency.

In some cases, mythological elements can be used to subvert or challenge traditional narratives. Angela Carter's *The Bloody Chamber*, for example, reimagines classic fairy tales through a feminist lens, using mythological elements to explore issues of gender and sexuality.

Overall, mythological elements continue to play an important role in contemporary English literature, providing writers with a rich source of inspiration and allowing them to explore universal themes in new and innovative ways

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